

Description of Supplementary Files for “Molecular and morphological baraminology of xenarthrans”

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SupplementaryFile1.xls: Character set from Billet et al., 2011, and results from BARCLAY analysis.

SupplementaryFile2.xls: Character set from Gaudin et al., 2004, and results from BARCLAY analysis.

SupplementaryFile3.xls: List of mtDNA accessions from NCBI and results from sequence analysis.